

Received 8 October 2025, accepted 16 November 2025, date of publication 24 November 2025,
date of current version 3 December 2025.

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3636417

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Equilibrium Analysis of Day-Ahead Electricity Markets With Strategic Demand Aggregators Based on the Theory of Learning in Games

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This work was supported by the Funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Program in the context of the EnerTEF Project under Agreement 101172887.

ABSTRACT Demand Aggregators (DAs) are expected to have a continuously increasing impact in the operation of modern electricity markets. Such players tend to concentrate large portfolios of demand-side resources, leading to market power concentration and imperfect competition. Such imperfectly competitive markets are analyzed in the literature by studying their equilibria. However, little attention has been given to the learning dynamics through which players adapt their bidding strategies over time and, crucially, to which equilibria are actually learnable. In this paper, we propose the coarse-correlated equilibrium as a solution concept that is more relevant than the Nash equilibrium for such markets. In contrast to the typical approach of the literature on Equilibrium Problems with Equilibrium Constraints, we model the learning dynamics that strategic DAs use to gradually optimize their bidding strategies. At the same time, in contrast to generic model-free approaches, we account for the fact that market players would make better use of the markets' available information by explicitly modeling their competitors. To that end, we propose a game-theoretic learning algorithm, in which each strategic DA observes the bids of its competitors and gradually builds beliefs about their bidding strategies. The resulting equilibria are compared to the pure Nash equilibria of the related literature. Our numerical results demonstrate that, in practice, strategic DAs can manipulate prices and market conditions to a greater extent than previously anticipated for the benefit of the energy system as a whole.

INDEX TERMS Equilibrium analysis, demand aggregator, bi-level optimization, EPEC, flexibility, learning in games.

NOMENCLATURE

Sets

N Set of transmission buses.
 H_i^{EV} Operating horizon of prosumer i 's EV,
 $H_i^{EV} = [t_i^{arr}, t_i^{dep}]$.

The associate editor coordinating the review of this manuscript and approving it for publication was Ayaz Ahmad¹.

L_n^{EV} Set of prosumers with EVs located at bus n .
 G Set of generators' buses, $G \subseteq N$.
 H Set of timeslots in the scheduling horizon, indexed by $t..$
 L_n^{INL} Set of prosumers with inflexible loads located at bus n .
 L Set of transmission lines L Set of transmission lines.

L_n^{RES} Set of prosumers with RES units located at bus n .
 D^c Set of buses with competing DAs' assets, $D^c \subseteq N$.
 L_n^{SL} Set of prosumers with SLs located at bus n .
 H_i^{TCL} Operating horizon of prosumer i 's TCL.
 L_n^{TCL} Set of prosumers with TCLs located at bus n .
 $X_{U/L}$ Set of upper/lower-level problem variables.

Decision Variables

b_{nt}/o_{nt} Strategic DA's quantity bid/offer (MW).
 $\hat{p}_{nt}^{\vee}/\hat{p}_{nt}^{\wedge}$ Power the DA at bus n sells/buys to/from the market at time t (MW).
 λ_{nt} Locational marginal price at bus n and time t (€/MW).
 ϕ_{it} Binary variable indicating the operation mode of prosumer i 's EV battery at time t .
 $p_{it}^{EV,\vee}/p_{it}^{EV,\wedge}$ Charging/Discharging power of prosumer i 's EV battery at bus n and time t (MW).
 SOC_{it} State-of-Charge of prosumer i 's EV battery at bus n and time t .
 g_{nt} Power produced by generator n and time t (MW).
 p_{it}^{INL} Power consumed by prosumer i 's inflexible load (MW) at time t .
 h_{nt} Binary variable indicating whether strategic DA at bus n submits a demand bid or a supply offer at time t .
 p_{it}^{RES} Power produced by prosumer i 's RES unit at time t (MW).
 $\bar{d}_{nt}^o/\bar{d}_{nt}^b$ Quantity offer/bid submitted by competing DA at bus n and time t (MW).
 ψ_{it} Binary variable indicating the On/Off status of prosumer i 's SL at time t .
 p_{it}^{SL} Power consumption of prosumer i 's SL at time t (MW).
 p_{it}^{TCL} Power consumption of prosumer i 's TCL at time t (MW).
 θ_{it} Indoors temperature of prosumer i at time t (°C).
 θ_{nt} Voltage phase angle of bus n at time t .

Parameters

θ_{it}^0 Outdoor (ambient) temperature of prosumer i at time t (°C).
 \mathcal{W} Large positive constant value.
 $\eta_i^{\vee}/\eta_i^{\wedge}$ Charging/discharging efficiency of prosumer i 's EV battery.
 COP_i Coefficient of performance of prosumer i 's TCL.
 C_i Thermal capacitance of prosumer i 's TCL (kWh/°C).
 \bar{T}_{ij} Capacity limit of transmission line ij (MW).
 c_{nt}^g Marginal production cost of generator n and time t (€/MW).
 \bar{G}_n Maximum production of generator n (MW).

P_{it}^{INL} Forecasted inflexible load profile of prosumer i 's inflexible load.
 SOC_{i0} Initial state-of-charge of prosumer i 's EV battery.
 SOC^{target} Requested state-of-charge level of prosumer i ' EV battery at the end of the scheduling horizon.
 $\bar{P}_i^{EV,\vee}/\bar{P}_i^{EV,\wedge}$ Maximum charging/discharging power limit of prosumer i 's EV battery (MW).
 $c_{nt}^{DA,\vee}$ Marginal utility of the strategic DA for consuming power at bus n and time t (€/MW).
 $c_{nt}^{DA,\wedge}$ Marginal cost of the strategic DA for producing power at bus n and time t (€/MW).
 y_{nj} Admittance of transmission line ij .
 P_{it}^{RES} Forecasted power production profile of prosumer i 's RES unit.
 d_{nt}^b Demand bids submitted by competing DA at bus n and time t (MW).
 d_{nt}^o Supply offer submitted by competing DA at bus n and time t (MW).
 $c_{nt}^{d,b}$ Marginal utility for consuming power of competing DA at bus n and time t (€/MW).
 $c_{nt}^{d,o}$ Marginal cost for supplying power of competing DA at bus n and time t (€/MW).
 R_i Thermal resistance of prosumer i 's TCL (°C/kW).
 P_{it}^{SL} Power consumption profile of prosumer i 's SL for each working cycle (MW).
 $\overline{SOC}_i/\underline{SOC}_i$ Upper/Lower limits on state-of-charge of prosumer i 's EV battery.
 \bar{P}_i^{TCL} TCL consumption power limit (MW).
 $\bar{\theta}_i/\underline{\theta}_i$ Maximum/minimum desired indoors temperature of prosumer i (°C).
 θ_{ref} Voltage phase angle of the reference bus.
 D_i The non-interruptible work cycle duration of prosumer i 's SL.

Dual Variables

ϕ Dual variables of the lower-level problem.

I. INTRODUCTION

In modern electricity markets, equilibrium analysis tools are increasingly important to study potential dangers of market gaming and inefficient market outcomes. From a policy maker's/regulator's perspective, market equilibrium analysis is essential to proactively anticipate potential market malfunctions and evaluate the participants' market power [1], [2]. When it comes to market power concentration, an increasingly important player is the Demand

Aggregator (DA): an intermediary between the wholesale market and multiple small-scale distributed energy resources (DERs), e.g. electric vehicles, thermostatically-controlled loads, shiftable loads, small RES units equipped with battery storage, etc. Aggregating large numbers of DERs under a single DA facilitates the predictability and controllability of the portfolio's aggregated energy consumption, as larger groups tend to smooth out individual fluctuations. This gives a large DA a competitive advantage, which drives consumers towards a few, large DAs. This, however, leads to market concentration and subsequent market power. To that end, it is expected that an imperfect market with a small number of large strategic DAs will prevail (see [1] and references therein).

The literature around analyzing imperfect-competition electricity markets is predominantly based on Equilibrium Programming with Equilibrium Constraints (EPEC) models. Such models adopt an iterative best-response algorithm, where each player iteratively solves its own profit-maximizing problem, formulated as a Mathematical Program with Equilibrium Constraints (MPEC). At each iteration, each player presumes that the bids of other players are fixed to their latest update, i.e. each player best-responds to the latest update of the others' bids. However, it is much more realistic to model players as gradual learners that adapt their strategies based on the whole history of play and available information, rather than as myopic best-responders. Thereupon, analyzing the resulting equilibria for the case of learning-based strategic DAs, emerges as a prevalent research gap in the existing literature.

In this paper, we address this gap by proposing the class of Coarse Correlated Equilibria (CCE), as a much more realistic solution concept for oligopolistic electricity markets with adaptive participants. Towards analyzing market equilibria of this class (instead of Nash equilibria that EPECs analyze), we consider the interaction of strategic DAs with learning capabilities. In particular, we provide an analysis using the Fictitious Play (FP) [3] algorithm to model the DAs' learning dynamics. The common element of FP models is that a player is assumed to respond optimally to an evolving belief on the behavior of its opponents, where the player's belief at any point in time is formed on the basis of the empirical frequencies of strategy choices made by its opponents up to that point [3]. The use of FP is particularly suitable for the electricity market's equilibrium analysis because in FP, players do not need to know anything at all about their opponents' payoffs, but they only need to form beliefs about how their opponents will play based on the opponent's historical actions (i.e., bids) [4]. FP is also a simple, practical, and easily interpretable baseline algorithm with desirable convergence properties to CCE [5], [6]. Finally, the proposed FP's MPEC-enhanced feature exploits all available information in today's electricity markets, while learning empirically from the entire history of play in a non-myopic manner.

II. RELATED WORKS AND PAPER CONTRIBUTIONS

Related works can be categorized into four main classes: (i) MPEC-related works, which focus on modeling a single strategic DA with numerous heterogeneous DERs; (ii) EPEC-related works, which focus on analyzing the market equilibrium resulting from the competition among several strategic DAs; (iii) multi-agent learning-based methods, which depart from the aforementioned MPEC/EPEC models and opt for more pragmatic considerations about the market players' bidding strategies; and (iv) FP-based learning studies, including both theoretical ones that provide the theoretical basis for our work and more practical ones that have been applied in domains other than the electricity markets.

A. MPEC-RELATED WORKS FOR A SINGLE STRATEGIC DA WITH NUMEROUS HETEROGENEOUS DERS

Early MPEC-related studies adopted a single utility function to capture the DA's aggregate flexibility capabilities, either by assuming a large-scale consumer or without modeling the various types of small-scale DERs that belong to the DA's portfolio (see [2] and references therein). For example, [7] considers a generic model for demand-side flexibility; however, the focus is not on the market power potential of the demand side. Works such as [8], [9], and [10] model a strategic DA that operates just one specific type of DERs, namely a fleet of distributed EVs, distributed curtailable loads and distributed battery storage units respectively. Finally, the works [11], [12], [13] model several types of heterogeneous DERs under the same DA. The focus of this literature is on maximizing a single strategic DA's profits, while assuming that all other players are price takers, thereby abstaining from conducting a market equilibrium analysis. In this paper, we use the MPEC problem formulation as the basic building block for modeling the strategic behavior of DAs that operate several types of small-scale DERs.

B. EPEC-RELATED WORKS FOR MODELING COMPETITION AMONG SEVERAL STRATEGIC DAs

A market equilibrium analysis is undertaken by EPEC-related works that model the competition among several strategic players. Among the first, [14] used the diagonalization (DIAG) method to find Nash equilibria in an imperfect electricity market with strategic generators. The authors in [15] and [16] focused on EPEC problem formulations by modeling several strategic Energy Storage System (ESS) operators and studying the potential impact that diverse types of ESSs may have on the market equilibrium.

When it comes to aggregators, studies [17] and [18] also perform a market equilibrium analysis by focusing on the interaction between a strategic ESS operator and a strategic DA. Both works only consider a generic model of the flexibility portfolio and do not explicitly model various types of DERs. Our own recent works [2], [19] studied the interaction of several strategic DAs, each with several types

of heterogeneous DERs, using the EPEC model. Finally, the EPEC problem in [20] focuses on modeling small-scale assets at the distribution network level without explicitly modeling flexible loads. Importantly, this literature models the bid-update strategy of each player as a *myopic best-response* to the latest observed choices of its competitors leading thus to a pure Nash equilibrium analysis. In this paper, we propose the class of Coarse Correlated Equilibrium (CCE) as a more realistic concept and compare it with the state-of-the-art EPEC-related works.

C. MULTI-AGENT LEARNING FOR STRATEGIC BIDDING AND MARKET EQUILIBRIUM ANALYSIS

Recently, several works have also undertaken the view that myopic best-response is not a realistic model of how real players learn to bid in electricity markets. Thereupon, learning-based approaches, informed by the whole history of play, have been proposed as an alternative to EPEC models.

The authors in [21] propose a Reinforcement Learning framework for a single player's bidding decisions. The study proposes the Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient algorithm and compares it with Q-learning and Deep Q-Network methods as well as the optimal MPEC-based solution (i.e. benchmark solution). Similarly, model-free approaches have been proposed for electricity market equilibrium analysis comparing them with the EPEC-based solution, which also serves as a benchmark. For example, in [22], [23] [24] and [25], theoretical frameworks are proposed in which multi-agent simulation and deep reinforcement learning methods are combined to analyze the market equilibrium. Finally, the authors in [26], adopted the Hedge algorithm to model the bidding behavior of strategic generators that incorporate the observed historical market outcomes into their strategy updates.

However, in this literature, each player learns by simply linking its own strategies to its own rewards, without modeling its competitors and how they change their own respective strategies. The fact that competitors also adapt their strategies, makes a player's learning problem non-stationary: a player's strategy at any given point is based on past experiences that may no longer reflect the updated market dynamics, which can easily lead to suboptimal player profits. Because of this, a real-world player is unlikely to rely solely on plain strategy-to-reward learning, and is instead expected to explicitly incorporate the information acquired about its competitors' strategies into its own bidding strategy learning dynamics like our MPEC-enhanced FP algorithm proposes.

D. FICTITIOUS PLAY-BASED LEARNING & OTHER OPPONENT MODELING STUDIES

Fictitious Play (FP) [3] has long served as a cornerstone in the study of adaptive learning in multi-agent systems. Classical works such as [27] and [28] rigorously establish convergence properties of FP in zero-sum and potential

games. Reference [29] extends these results to asymmetric $2 \times n$ games, while [6] connects FP to no-regret dynamics, revealing that FP trajectories converge to Coarse Correlated Equilibrium (CCE) under general conditions.

Building upon these theoretical foundations, FP has been proposed for diverse domains other than electricity markets. For example, in decentralized wireless networks' domain, [30] tests several learning techniques to enable wireless devices to learn equilibrium strategies with only partial information. It is shown that the standard FP algorithm and its smoothed FP variant can outperform best-response dynamics and model-free solutions. In intelligent transportation systems, [31] utilizes joint strategy fictitious play (JSFP) to solve dynamic route guidance problems, where drivers incorporate past travel times into their route selection process (cf. how DAs must make repeated bidding decisions, while learning from historical electricity market outcomes). In vehicular networks, [32] show that integrating FP algorithm within a multi-agent reinforcement learning framework significantly enhances both system-wide resource utilization and individual agent performance in highly dynamic environments. Furthermore, [33] analyzes continuous-time FP in arbitrary network games. They demonstrate convergence to Nash equilibria under structural assumptions such as zero-sum interactions, potential games and acyclic network topologies, providing theoretical backing for FP-based dynamics in graph-structured multi-agent environments (cf. zonal electricity markets in this paper's context).

Finally, there are many opponent modeling related works in the international literature, which are much more sophisticated and complex than FP. For example, bayesian learning or multi-agent inverse reinforcement learning frameworks may be used when more information about opponents is available, more hidden preferences and latent variables need to be incorporated or when opponent strategies are quickly evolving [34]. In this work, our focus is on identifying learnable equilibria in electricity markets taking into account that only historical datasets about opponent's bidding actions and market results are available.

E. PAPER CONTRIBUTIONS

Two main paradigms for analyzing the emerging behavior of electricity market participants have been analyzed: the EPEC paradigm (i.e. subsection II-B) and the strategy-reward learning paradigm (i.e. subsection II-C). The former does not account for the fact that players would learn from the whole history of play, while the latter does not account for the fact that players would try to improve their strategies' performance by also modeling their competitors as well as the known mechanism of the market clearing process.

In this paper, we bridge this gap by considering learning-adaptive players, who also model their competitors explicitly. Furthermore, we apply this concept to an electricity market with strategic DAs, explicitly modeling the underlying DERs of each DA's portfolio. We propose the notion of Coarse

Correlated Equilibrium (CCE) as a solution concept that is more relevant than the Nash Equilibrium. We thereby analyze CCE for oligopolistic electricity markets with learning-assisted adaptive DAs. The paper's contributions can be summarized as follows:

- In contrast to the EPEC-based related works (cf. subsection II-B), which assume that a strategic DA myopically best-responds to the latest update of the rivals' bids (cf. diagonalization algorithm), we consider that each strategic DA observes the rivals' market participation strategies and gradually learns to anticipate their bidding strategies. Such an approach lends from the rich theory of Learning in Games [4]. We thereby propose the Fictitious Play algorithm [3] towards modeling the evolution of the DAs' bidding strategies. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work that proposes CCE as a solution concept for electricity market equilibrium analysis and the first FP-based analysis, where players explicitly model opponent bidding behavior in a bi-level optimization market clearing context.
- We also explicitly model the heterogeneous DERs of each strategic DA's portfolio and simulate a multi-agent system that models the learning dynamics of the multi-agent learning game and study the resulting CCE. Interestingly, we find that, in this model, strategic DAs can exert greater market influence compared to a Nash equilibrium model.
- Finally, our simulation results provide valuable policy insights regarding the potential benefits of the proposed CCE in real electricity markets (i.e. increase of social welfare, decrease of system's marginal prices, counter-balance of large suppliers' market power), if the DAs had access to more information regarding the historical bidding data of their competitors.

We begin by modeling the bidding optimization problem of a single DA (Section III) and proceed to present the Nash and Coarse-Correlated equilibrium algorithms in Section IV. Section V presents a comparative numerical evaluation and Section VI concludes by discussing relevant policy implications.

III. SINGLE DA PROBLEM

In this section, we model a single DA responsible for managing a portfolio of DERs. Each DER is located under a transmission network bus $n \in N^m$, where N^m is the set of transmission network buses in which the DA has presence. The DERs include Electric Vehicles-EVs (set L_n^{EV}), Thermostatically Controlled Loads (L_n^{TCL}), shiftable loads (L_n^{SL}), inflexible loads (L_n^{INL}) and Renewable Energy Sources (L_n^{RES}). The DA serves as an intermediary between its portfolio of prosumers and the day-ahead electricity market, submitting both demand bids and supply offers. We assume quantity-only bids, as is typically the case in practice for DAs and suppliers. By managing a sufficiently large and diverse

portfolio of flexible prosumers, the DA can potentially influence price formation in the market clearing process.

We consider that the DA models the market clearing process and its competitors' strategies into its bidding optimization problem. Thus, the DA's bidding problem is formulated as an MPEC, i.e. a bi-level optimization problem. In the upper level, the DA seeks to minimize its cost from market participation, while respecting the operational constraints of its portfolio. The lower-level problem represents the market clearing process, which determines market outcomes such as market prices, generation dispatch and demand allocation. We consider a day-ahead, nodal, network-constrained electricity pool market with a 24-hour time horizon (H), which governs the operation of a transmission system. The transmission system is characterized by a set of buses N and a set of transmission lines L . Both generators and DAs participate in the market.

A. UPPER-LEVEL PROBLEM: DA'S PROFIT MAXIMIZATION

In the upper-level problem, the DA minimizes its electricity procurement cost (a.1). The Locational Marginal Price (LMP) at node $n \in N^m$ and timeslot t is denoted by λ_{nt} . The energy sold to, or purchased from, the pool market at timeslot t are represented by p_{nt}^{\wedge} and p_{nt}^{\vee} , respectively. Both the LMPs and the power traded by the DA are endogenously determined by the lower-level problem.

$$\min_{\mathbb{X}_U} \sum_{n \in N^m} \sum_{t \in H} \lambda_{nt} \cdot (p_{nt}^{\vee} - p_{nt}^{\wedge}) \quad (a.1)$$

Subject to : EV Constraints

$$0 \leq p_{it}^{EV, \vee} \leq \phi_{it} \cdot \bar{P}_i^{EV, \vee}, \forall i \in L_n^{EV}, n \in N^m, t \in H_i^{EV}, \quad (a.2)$$

$$0 \leq p_{it}^{EV, \wedge} \leq (1 - \phi_{it}) \cdot \bar{P}_i^{EV, \wedge}, \forall i \in L_n^{EV}, n \in N^m, t \in H_i^{EV} \quad (a.3)$$

$$\phi_{it} \in \{0, 1\}, \forall i \in L_n^{EV}, n \in N^m, t \in H_i^{EV} \quad (a.4)$$

$$SOC_{i(t+1)} = SOC_{it} + \eta_i^{\vee} \cdot p_{it}^{EV, \vee} - \frac{p_{it}^{EV, \wedge}}{\eta_i^{\wedge}}, \quad i \in L_n^{EV}, n \in N^m, t \in H_i^{EV} \quad (a.5)$$

$$SOC_{it} = SOC_{i0}, \forall i \in L_n^{EV}, n \in N^m, t \in H_i^{EV} \quad (a.6)$$

$$SOC_{it} = SOC^{target}, \forall i \in L_n^{EV}, n \in N^m, t \in H_i^{EV} \quad (a.7)$$

$$\underline{SOC}_i \leq SOC_{it} \leq \overline{SOC}_i, \forall i \in L_n^{EV}, n \in N^m, t \in H_i^{EV} \quad (a.8)$$

Constraints (a.2) - (a.8) pertain to the operation of the EVs in the DA's portfolio. Each EV $i \in L_n^{EV}$ is assumed to have user-defined parameters, including a preferred plug-in time (t_i^{arr}), departure time (t_i^{dep}), and desired State-of-Charge (SoC) at the end of the plug-in period ($H_i^{EV} = [t_i^{arr}, t_i^{dep}]$). Constraints (a.2) and (a.3) impose limits on the charging and discharging power of EV i ($\bar{P}_i^{EV, \vee}, \bar{P}_i^{EV, \wedge}$). The binary

variable ϕ_{it} in constraint (a.4) ensures that simultaneous charging and discharging are prevented. Constraint (a.5) defines the SoC of EV i (SOC_{it}) at any time, calculated based on the previous hour SoC, as well as the charging/discharging amounts ($p_{it}^{EV,\downarrow}, p_{it}^{EV,\uparrow}$) and associated efficiencies ($\eta_i^{\downarrow}, \eta_i^{\uparrow}$). The initial SoC is defined by constraint (a.6), with SOC_{i0} representing the initial SoC. Constraint (a.7) requires that the SoC reach the user-specified level (SOC^{target}) by departure time. Finally, constraint (a.8) bounds the SoC within the lower and upper limits ($\underline{SOC}_i, \overline{SOC}_i$).

TCL Constraints

$$0 \leq p_{it}^{TCL} \leq \overline{P}_i^{TCL}, \forall i \in L_n^{TCL}, n \in N^m, t \in H_i^{TCL} \quad (a.9)$$

$$\theta_{i(t+1)} = \beta_i \cdot \theta_{it} + (1 - \beta_i) \cdot (\theta_{it}^0 + COP_i \cdot R_i \cdot p_{it}^{TCL}),$$

$$\beta_i = e^{-\frac{\Delta t}{C_i \cdot R_i}}, \forall i \in L_n^{TCL}, n \in N^m, t \in H_i^{TCL} \quad (a.10)$$

$$\underline{\theta}_i \leq \theta_{it} \leq \overline{\theta}_i, \forall i \in L_n^{TCL}, n \in N^m, t \in H_i^{TCL} \quad (a.11)$$

Constraints (a.9) – (a.11) govern the operation of each TCL $i \in L_n^{TCL}$, operating over a time interval $H_i^{TCL} \subseteq T$, set by the user. The upper bound on power consumption (\overline{P}_i^{TCL}) is enforced by constraint (a.9). The indoor temperature dynamics for each TCL are captured by constraint (a.10), considering parameters such as thermal resistance R_i ($^{\circ}C/kW$), capacitance C_i ($kWh/^{\circ}C$), the coefficient of performance COP_i , and outdoor temperature θ_{it}^0 . Constraint (a.11) ensures that TCL owners can specify minimum ($\underline{\theta}_i$) and maximum ($\overline{\theta}_i$) allowable indoor temperatures.

Shiftable Load Constraints

$$p_{it}^{SL} = \sum_{\tau=t-D_i+1}^t (\psi_{i\tau} \cdot Pr_{ik}), \forall i \in L_n^{SL}, n \in N^m, t \geq T_i^{SL,a},$$

$$k = (t - \tau) \bmod D_i \quad (a.12)$$

$$\psi_{it} = 0, \forall i \in L_n^{SL}, n \in N^m, t < T_i^{SL,a}, t > T_i^{SL,b} - D_i + 2 \quad (a.13)$$

$$\sum_{t=T_i^{SL,a}}^{T_i^{SL,b}} \psi_{it} = 1, \forall i \in L_n^{SL}, n \in N^m \quad (a.14)$$

Shiftable loads (SLs) $i \in L_n^{SL}$ operate with a predefined consumption profile \mathbf{Pr}_i over a working cycle with duration D_i . For example, if a task lasts for 2 hours and consumes 2 kW each hour, the consumption profile would be [2 kW (hour 1), 2 kW (hour 2)]. Owners specify the earliest possible start time ($T_i^{SL,a}$) and the latest completion time ($T_i^{SL,b}$). Constraint (a.12) defines the electric power consumption of SL i at each hour $t \in [T_i^{SL,a}, T_i^{SL,b}]$, with the binary variable ψ_{it} indicating whether the SL starts operation at hour t . Constraint (a.13) ensures that the SL neither starts outside the user-defined interval $[T_i^{SL,a}, T_i^{SL,b}]$ nor at a time that would prevent task completion by $T_i^{SL,b}$. Constraint (a.14) enforces that the SL can only begin once during its working

cycle.

Renewable Energy Generation

$$0 \leq p_{it}^{RES} \leq Pr_{it}^{RES}, \forall i \in L_n^{RES}, n \in N^m, t \in H \quad (a.15)$$

The renewable energy production of each RES unit $i \in L_n^{RES}$ is constrained by the forecasted production profile (Pr_{it}^{RES}) as specified by constraint (a.15). Note that renewable energy spillage is allowed.

Inflexible Loads

$$p_{it}^{INL} = Pr_{it}^{INL}, \forall i \in L_n^{INL}, n \in N^m, t \in H \quad (a.16)$$

Constraint (a.16) states that the consumption of each inflexible load $i \in L_n^{INL}$ must follow its forecasted power profile (Pr_{it}^{INL}).

DA Portfolio's Power Balance

$$p_{nt}^{\downarrow} - p_{nt}^{\uparrow} = \sum_{i \in L_n^{EV}} (p_{it}^{EV,\downarrow} - p_{it}^{EV,\uparrow}) + \sum_{i \in L_n^{TCL}} p_{it}^{TCL} + \sum_{i \in L_n^{SL}} p_{it}^{SL} + \sum_{i \in L_n^{INL}} p_{it}^{INL} - \sum_{i \in L_n^{RES}} p_{it}^{RES}, \forall n \in N^m, t \in H \quad (a.17)$$

Constraint (a.17) ensures that the final DA dispatch at each timeslot t and bus $n \in N^m$ equals the combined power output of all assets at that specific bus.

DA's Supply Offers/Demand Bids

$$0 \leq b_{nt} \leq h_{nt} \cdot \mathcal{W}, \forall n \in N^m, t \in H \quad (a.18)$$

$$0 \leq o_{nt} \leq (1 - h_{nt}) \cdot \mathcal{W}, \forall n \in N^m, t \in H \quad (a.19)$$

$$h_{nt} \in \{0, 1\}, \forall n \in N^m, t \in H \quad (a.20)$$

Finally, constraints (a.18) and (a.19) prevent simultaneous submission of demand (b_{nt}) and supply (o_{nt}) bids in the market, with \mathcal{W} representing a large constant value. Finally, constraint (a.20) defines the binary nature of the auxiliary variable h_{nt} . The set of decision variables in the DA's upper-level problem is $\mathbb{X}_U = \{o_{nt}, b_{nt}, h_{nt}, p_{it}^{EV,\downarrow}, p_{it}^{EV,\uparrow}, \phi_{it}, SOC_{it}, p_{it}^{TCL}, \theta_{it}, p_{it}^{SL}, \psi_{it}, p_{it}^{RES}, p_{it}^{INL}\}$.

B. LOWER-LEVEL PROBLEM: DAY-AHEAD MARKET CLEARING

In the lower level, the Market Operator clears the day-ahead electricity market based on the offers/bids submitted by the market participants. The market clearing process that follows uses a DC approximation of the network.

$$\min_{\mathbb{X}_L} \sum_{t \in H} \left\{ \sum_{n \in G} c_{nt}^g \cdot g_{nt} + \sum_{n \in DC} (c_{nt}^{d,o} \cdot d_{nt}^o - c_{nt}^{d,b} \cdot d_{nt}^b) + \sum_{n \in N^m} (c_{nt}^{DA,\uparrow} \cdot p_{nt}^{\uparrow} - c_{nt}^{DA,\downarrow} \cdot p_{nt}^{\downarrow}) \right\} \quad (b.1)$$

$$\text{Subject to } -g_{nt} + d_{nt}^b - d_{nt}^o + p_{nt}^{\vee} - \bar{p}_{nt}^{\wedge} + \sum_{j \neq i} y_{nj} \cdot (\theta_{ni} - \theta_{jt}) = 0; (\lambda_{nt}) \quad \forall n \in N, t \in H \quad (\text{b.2})$$

$$0 \leq g_{nt} \leq \bar{G}_n; (\underline{\phi}_{nt}^g, \bar{\phi}_{nt}^g) \quad \forall n \in G, t \in H \quad (\text{b.3})$$

$$0 \leq \bar{p}_{nt}^{\wedge} \leq o_{nt}; (\underline{\phi}_{nt}^{DAo}, \bar{\phi}_{nt}^{DAo}) \quad \forall n \in N^m, t \in H \quad (\text{b.4})$$

$$0 \leq p_{nt}^{\vee} \leq b_{nt}; (\underline{\phi}_{nt}^{DAb}, \bar{\phi}_{nt}^{DAb}) \quad \forall n \in N^m, t \in H \quad (\text{b.5})$$

$$0 \leq d_{nt}^o \leq \bar{d}_{nt}^o; (\underline{\phi}_{nt}^{do}, \bar{\phi}_{nt}^{do}) \quad \forall n \in D^c, t \in H \quad (\text{b.6})$$

$$0 \leq d_{nt}^b \leq \bar{d}_{nt}^b; (\underline{\phi}_{nt}^{db}, \bar{\phi}_{nt}^{db}) \quad \forall n \in D^c, t \in H \quad (\text{b.7})$$

$$-\bar{T}_{ij} \leq y_{nj} \cdot (\theta_{ni} - \theta_{jt}) \leq \bar{T}_{ij}; (\underline{\phi}_{(nj)t}^l, \bar{\phi}_{(nj)t}^l) \quad \forall (n, j) \in L, t \in H \quad (\text{b.8})$$

The operator aims to maximize *Social Welfare*, or equivalently, minimize the *Social Cost*, defined as the total cost of energy generation minus the demand's willingness to pay for that energy (constraint (b.1)). This calculation is based on the marginal costs of generators (c_{nt}^g) and the marginal cost/utility functions of DAs ($c_{nt}^{DA, \bar{\vee}}, c_{nt}^{d, o}, c_{nt}^{DA, \vee}, c_{nt}^{d, b}$). Power balance at each bus $n \in N$ and hour $t \in H$ is enforced by constraint (b.2), with the corresponding dual variables representing the nodal LMPs (λ_{nt}). The maximum generation capacity of each generator $n \in G$ is defined by constraint (b.3). The strategic DA's dispatch, whether selling (\bar{p}_{nt}^{\wedge}) or purchasing (p_{nt}^{\vee}) power, is bounded by constraints (b.4) and (b.5) based on its submitted offers and bids. Constraints (b.6) and (b.7) apply to competing DAs (D^c), constraining the power they can either supply (d_{nt}^o) or draw (d_{nt}^b) from the transmission grid based on their respective offer and bid quantities ($\bar{d}_{nt}^o, \bar{d}_{nt}^b$). Lastly, Constraint (b.8) ensures that power flows remain within the transmission lines' capacity limits (\bar{T}_{ij}). The dual variables associated with each constraint in the lower-level problem are specified after the semicolon in each equation. Additionally, the voltage phase angle at the reference bus is fixed to zero throughout the entire scheduling period ($\theta_{ref} = 0$). The decision variable set for the optimization problem (b) is given by $\mathbb{X}_L = \{g_{nt}, d_{nt}^o, d_{nt}^b, \bar{p}_{nt}^{\wedge}, p_{nt}^{\vee}, \theta_{nt}\}$.

C. MPEC SOLUTION METHOD

The formulated non-linear bi-level optimization problem can be transformed into a Mathematical Program with Equilibrium Constraints (MPEC). This transformation is achieved by replacing problem (b) with its corresponding Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions. Since this problem is continuous and linear, its KKT conditions serve as both necessary and sufficient optimality conditions [35]. The resulting single-level problem introduces non-linear complementarity slackness conditions. To handle these non-linearities, we apply

the Big-M method, a well-established technique successfully employed in similar contexts, as discussed in [10] and [12].

Additionally, the objective function of the DA's problem (a.1) presents further challenges due to its inherent non-linearity. To address this, we utilize the Strong Duality Theorem, along with the optimality conditions of the lower-level problem, performing a series of algebraic manipulations. This reformulation transforms the bi-level profit maximization problem into a Mixed-Integer Linear Program (MILP), which can be efficiently solved using off-the-shelf solvers. For a detailed step-by-step explanation of the procedure used to convert the bi-level problem into a MILP, the interested reader is referred to our previous work in [2], where the methodology and its implementation are thoroughly discussed.

IV. MULTIPLE STRATEGIC DAs AND EQUILIBRIA

In this section, we explore equilibrium concepts for strategic demand aggregators (DAs) in electricity market bidding. We present the standard Equilibrium Problem with Equilibrium Constraints (EPEC) model, commonly used to analyze Nash Equilibria (NE) (subsection IV-A), and propose a Coarse Correlated Equilibria (CCE) solution concept, where players adapt their strategies based on the historical behavior of competitors (subsection IV-B). In contrast to the learning-based literature (reviewed in Section II-C), we consider players that explicitly model their competitors. Each approach involves an iterative process where DAs solve their Mathematical Programs with Equilibrium Constraints (MPECs), derived from bilevel problems (a-b). The crucial difference between the two models lies in how each player updates the expected strategy of each competitor's expected strategies: the EPEC literature uses the competitor's latest strategy, while the CCE model uses the empirical distribution of all past strategies.

A. BEST-RESPONSE TOWARDS NASH EQUILIBRIA

In the EPEC literature, a best-response (diagonalization) algorithm is adopted where each player iteratively solves its own MPEC, treating the bids and offers of other DAs as fixed parameters based on their most recent choices. This process continues until all DAs' decision variables stabilize within a tolerance ϵ , indicating convergence to an ϵ -equilibrium. The procedure is presented in Algorithm 1.

B. COARSE CORRELATED EQUILIBRIA (CCE)

Obtaining provable convergence to a Nash Equilibrium (NE) in general classes of games remains challenging due to several inherent difficulties. Players may struggle to coordinate around one specific equilibrium, especially when multiple equilibria exist while, in some cases, there may be no pure NE strategy at all. Moreover, computing a NE is generally intractable [36]. Thereby, if a NE cannot be computed (reproduced in a simulation environment), it is unjustified to expect that the market will discover it [37].

Given these considerations-i.e., potential absence of pure NE, and computational intractability-the CCE emerges as

Algorithm 1 Diagonalization Algorithm

- 1: *Initialization:*
 - Set convergence tolerance ϵ .
 - Set maximum number of iterations K .
 - Set iteration counter $\kappa \leftarrow 1$.
 - DAs' offers/bids ($\hat{d}_{n,t}^o/\hat{d}_{n,t}^b$) are initialized.
- 2: For $j = 1, \dots, |D^c| + 1$
 - DA j solves its MPEC problem, considering the offers/bids of the other DAs as fixed parameters ($\hat{d}_{j',t}^o/\hat{d}_{j',t}^b$, where $j' \in D^c$), equal to their values at iteration $\kappa - 1$.
 - DA j obtains $o_{n,t}^{(\kappa)}, b_{n,t}^{(\kappa)}$, where $n \in N_j^m$.
- 3: If $|o_{n,t}^{(\kappa)} - o_{n,t}^{(\kappa-1)}| \leq \epsilon$ and $|b_{n,t}^{(\kappa)} - b_{n,t}^{(\kappa-1)}| \leq \epsilon$ for all $j \in \{1, \dots, |D^c| + 1\}$, $n \in D^c$, $t \in H$ then quit and report the last solution from Step 2.
- 4: if $\kappa = K$ quit and report that the algorithm has failed to converge. Report the last solution from Step 2.
- 5: Set $\kappa \leftarrow \kappa + 1$ and return to Step 2.

a more pragmatic solution concept. Unlike NE, CCE is defined relative to a joint probability distribution over possible actions and does not face the same computational barriers. Furthermore, it is guaranteed to exist for any finite game. Thus, CCE provides a more accessible framework for modeling strategic behavior. Moreover, the myopic best-response model described in the previous subsection implicitly assumes participants that update their strategy based solely on the most recent updates from the other participants. However, in practical settings, actual strategic market participants typically incorporate past experience into their current domain knowledge. This approach acknowledges that participants do not operate in isolation from past events but adapt, through learning patterns, and anticipate the strategies of others over time. Thus, participants may progressively develop sophisticated behavioral models that inform their strategic adjustments.

To capture this dynamic aspect of strategic learning, we propose an MPEC-enhanced Fictitious Play (FP) algorithm, where DAs adjust their strategies using the empirical distribution of competitors' historical actions (i.e. bids/offers). This approach aligns with the CCE concept, as FP's empirical frequency of play converges to a CCE [5], [6], providing a practical equilibrium approximation.

FP is a classical game-theoretic learning algorithm, where players iteratively adjust their strategies based on the historical actions of their rivals. The fundamental assumption behind FP is that each player perceives the rivals' strategies as stationary over time and updates its best response according to the empirical distribution of observed plays. A key characteristic of FP is that it does not require players to have complete information about the rivals' profit functions or strategies. Instead, players learn by observing the historical

outcomes of the game and just form beliefs about how their rivals will play.

In our context, DAs act as strategic players, who optimize their bidding and offering strategies over multiple rounds of interaction. In iteration k , each DA i discretizes the quantity offer ($\bar{d}_{jt}^{o,(k)}$) and bid ($\bar{d}_{jt}^{b,(k)}$) variables of each competing DA j and timeslot t into finite sets of V discrete values $\mathbf{O}_{jt} = \{\bar{d}_{jt}^o[v]\}_{v \in \mathcal{V}}$ and $\mathbf{B}_{jt} = \{\bar{d}_{jt}^b[v]\}_{v \in \mathcal{V}}$. Note that $\mathcal{V} = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, V\}$ represents the set of discrete values available for the offer and bid variables. Let $\ell_{j,t,v}(k)$ denote the number of times DA j has chosen action v at timeslot t up to and including iteration k . The counter for each action is updated as follows:

$$\ell_{j,t,v}(k) = \ell_{j,t,v}(k-1) + 1 \quad (\text{c.1})$$

To approximate the stationary mixed strategy of DA j , DA i maintains an empirical distribution over j 's past actions. Specifically, let $\pi_{j,t,v}(k)$ denote DA i 's belief at iteration k about the probability that DA j will choose strategy v at timeslot t . This empirical probability is updated using the following equation:

$$\pi_{j,v,t}(k) = \frac{\ell_{j,v,t}(k)}{\sum_{\hat{v} \in \mathcal{V}} \ell_{j,\hat{v},t}(k)} \quad (\text{c.2})$$

where the denominator sums over all possible actions v that DA j could have taken at timeslot t .

At each iteration k , DA i chooses its new offers and bids by solving its MPEC problem, where the offers and bids of its competing DAs are considered to be the expected values from the empirical distributions:

$$\bar{d}_{jt}^{o,(k)} = \sum_{v \in \mathcal{V}} \pi_{j,v,t}(k) \cdot \bar{d}_{j,t}^o[v] \quad (\text{c.3})$$

$$\bar{d}_{jt}^{b,(k)} = \sum_{v \in \mathcal{V}} \pi_{j,v,t}(k) \cdot \bar{d}_{j,t}^b[v] \quad (\text{c.4})$$

This process continues iteratively, in a similar fashion to Algorithm 1, but with the difference that each DA best-responds to the empirical strategies of others based on their past behavior. The FP procedure is presented in Algorithm 2.

V. EVALUATION SETUP AND RESULTS

A. SIMULATION SETUP

In this section, we provide and discuss results derived from a case study based on a 6-Bus test system [12]. This system includes four conventional generators (G1-G4) and four DAs (DA1-D4), which are distributed across various buses as shown in Figure 1. The technical characteristics of the thermal generators are presented in Table 1. To simplify our analysis, we assume that all the end prosumers associated with a given DA are located at a single bus of the transmission system. The DAs participate in a typical day-ahead electricity market, placing their hourly bids for each of the 24 market hours, corresponding to the hours from 00:00 am to 11:00 pm.

Algorithm 2 Fictitious Play (FP) Algorithm

1: Initialization:

- Set convergence tolerance ϵ .
- Set maximum number of iterations K .
- Set iteration counter $\kappa \leftarrow 1$.
- Set discretization value \mathcal{V}
- Set $\ell_{j,v,t}^o$ and $\ell_{j,v,t}^b$ to zero for all $j \in \{1, \dots, |D^c| + 1\}$, $t \in H$, $v \in \mathcal{V}$
- Set $\pi_{j,v,t}^o$ and $\pi_{j,v,t}^b$ to zero for all $j \in \{1, \dots, |D^c| + 1\}$, $t \in H$, $v \in \mathcal{V}$
- DAs' offers/bids ($\hat{a}_{n,t}^o/\hat{a}_{n,t}^b$) are initialized.

2: For $j = 1, \dots, |D^c| + 1$

- DA j solves its MPEC problem, considering the offers/bids of the other DAs as fixed parameters ($\hat{a}_{j',t}^o/\hat{a}_{j',t}^b$, where $j' \in D^c$), equal to their values at iteration $\kappa - 1$.
- DA j obtains $o_{n,t}^{(\kappa)}$, $b_{n,t}^{(\kappa)}$, where $n \in N_j^m$.

3: Compute empirical probabilities:

$$\pi_{j,v,t}(\kappa) = \frac{\ell_{j,t,v}(\kappa)}{\sum_{\hat{v} \in \mathcal{V}} \ell_{j,t,\hat{v}}(\kappa)}$$

4: Compute expected aggregate strategies:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{d}_{j,t}^{o,(\kappa)} &= \sum_{v \in \mathcal{V}} \pi_{j,v,t}(\kappa) \cdot d_{j,t}^o[v], \\ \bar{d}_{j,t}^{b,(\kappa)} &= \sum_{v \in \mathcal{V}} \pi_{j,v,t}(\kappa) \cdot d_{j,t}^b[v] \end{aligned}$$

- 5: If $|o_{n,t}^{(\kappa)} - o_{n,t}^{(\kappa-1)}| \leq \epsilon$ and $|b_{n,t}^{(\kappa)} - b_{n,t}^{(\kappa-1)}| \leq \epsilon$ for all $j \in \{1, \dots, |D^c| + 1\}$, $n \in D^c$, $t \in H$ Stop and return current strategies as CCE solution from Step 2.
- 6: if $\kappa = K$ quit and report that the algorithm has failed to converge. Report the last solution from Step 2.
- 7: Set $\kappa \leftarrow \kappa + 1$ and return to Step 2.

TABLE 1. Thermal generators' technical parameters.

Generating Unit	Capacity (MW)	Marginal Generation Cost (€/MWh)
G1	100	15
G2	75	30
G3	50	60
G4	50	90

As discussed in section III, each DA manages a portfolio composed of EVs, TCLs, SLs, INLs and PV units. The portfolio's characteristics of each DA are summarized in Table 2. Furthermore, we have made the following assumptions regarding the composition and operation of each DA's portfolio:

- Each DA manages a portfolio consisting of 8,400 prosumers. Each prosumer possesses an EV, a shiftable load and a TCL device.
- EVs' plug-in times are uniformly distributed between 06:00 AM and 12:00 PM, with desired departure times

FIGURE 1. 6-Bus test system.

randomly selected within the interval of 4:00 PM to 10:00 PM. The aggregate nominal charging capacity of the EV fleet of each DA is approximately 50 MW, with 50% of the EVs in each DA's portfolio being V2G-capable.

- SL start times are distributed between 01:00-11:00 AM and 03:00-10:00 PM, with their task completion times occurring between 05:00 AM - 01:00 PM and 04:00-11:00 PM. The aggregate nominal power consumption of SLs is shown in Table 2.
- For TCLs, indoor temperature setpoints have a lower bound randomly selected between 19°C and 23°C, while the upper bound varies between 26°C and 30°C, reflecting user preferences.

TABLE 2. DA portfolio load across 24 hours.

DA Number	INL load (MWh)	EVs load (MWh)	SLs load (MWh)
1	1121.06	51.399	135.708
2	1129.815	51.047	136.797
3	1109.470	50.631	130.157
4	1099.724	52.423	122.639

Finally, price bids from DAs are set at 150€/MWh, in order to ensure that they can always be cleared in the electricity market. The interested reader can find a complete set of input data in [38]. The algorithm is implemented in Python using the Pyomo library. All optimization problems were solved using Gurobi. All tests were conducted on an Intel i5@2.9 GHz with 8 GB RAM.

B. CASE STUDY RESULTS

In this section, we analyze the outcomes of different market equilibrium scenarios in an electricity market setting with strategic DAs. The scenarios considered include:

- 1) **Competitive Market:** The welfare-maximizing dispatch is obtained by solving a centralized optimization problem, incorporating the constraints of all DERs. This is equivalent to the welfare-maximizing dispatch that would have resulted if the market was perfectly competitive.
- 2) **Nash-Cournot Equilibrium (Diagonalization):** This scenario models an electricity market with oligopolistic characteristics as an EPEC problem. The Nash-Cournot

equilibrium is obtained through a diagonalization algorithm, where each DA iteratively solves its own MPEC problem (cf. Section III). Each DA makes decisions based solely on its own profit maximization, assuming that its competitors will continue to follow the bidding strategies they adopted in the previous iteration. Note that in case the diagonalization algorithm fails to fully converge within a preset maximum number of iterations, all results reported are taken from the final iteration of the algorithm. This approach provides a practical approximation of the market equilibrium.

- 3) **Coarse Correlated Equilibrium (Fictitious Play):** In this oligopolistic market scenario, the CCE is obtained using the MPEC-enhanced FP algorithm. Each DA iteratively adjusts its strategy based on the observed historical actions of other DAs, gradually learning the best response to the accumulated historical behavior.

In the analysis of learning algorithms within the EPEC framework, the comparisons are based on three key metrics: social welfare, Demand Aggregators' (DAs) costs, and System Marginal Prices (SMPs). Social welfare is used as a market-efficiency indicator and is defined as the sum of DAs' surplus and generators' surplus—or, equivalently (see Section III-B), as the demand's willingness to pay for energy minus the total cost of generating that energy. DAs' costs denote the payments that DAs make for the energy purchased in the electricity market. System Marginal Prices are the market-clearing prices derived from the dual variables associated with the system-wide energy-balance constraint in the market-clearing problem ((b.2)). These are important metrics for market dynamics and equilibrium outcomes. To ensure a fair comparison and simulate realistic market conditions, all algorithms are initialized using the results from the Competitive model. This common starting point serves as an initial forecast of competitors' strategies, providing a consistent baseline for evaluating the performance and evolution of each algorithm within the EPEC framework.

TABLE 3. Social Welfare and Cost of the algorithms compared to the competitive model.

	Competitive	Diagonalization	FP
Social Welfare	641175.51€	620371.84€	627022.41€
<i>Difference</i>	—	-3.25%	-2.21%
Total DAs Cost	402835.07€	369404.66€	341046.31€
<i>Difference</i>	—	-8.30%	-15.34%
Generators' Profit	234763.33€	207895.14€	172840.61€
<i>Difference</i>	—	-11.45%	-26.38%

Table 3 presents our main result: the social welfare, the aggregate DAs' electricity costs, as well as the total generators' net profits, resulting from the different market scenarios. The competitive market scenario, representing an idealized benchmark with truthfully bidding players, naturally yields the highest social welfare at 641,176€. This

reflects the most efficient allocation of resources without any strategic distortions. In this context, the DAs' costs are the highest ones (402,835€), since they are considered to adopt competitive behavior, and the total net generators' payoffs amount to 234,763€.

The diagonalization algorithm results in lower (by 3.25%) social welfare compared to the competitive market. This decrease is due to the strategic behavior of the DAs, who manipulate their quantity bids to maximize individual profits rather than the overall system's welfare. DAs' costs are reduced compared to the competitive market by 8.30%, as they can strategically bid to minimize their market costs, reducing the net generators' profits by 11.45%, at the expense of overall social welfare. These numerical changes highlight the direct impact of strategic DA behavior on the market: the reduction in social welfare results from DAs prioritizing individual profit over system efficiency, while the decrease in net generators' profits arises because lower bids and shifted consumption reduce market prices (cf. also detailed dispatch results in appendix). This is also evident in Figure 2, which compares the hourly bids in the Nash-Cournot equilibrium (cf. DIAG) to those in a competitive market. As shown, DAs attempt to minimize market costs by reducing consumption during most timeslots, leveraging the flexibility offered by their controllable assets. The charging of EVs and operation of SLs is shifted from high-cost to low-cost hours.

Finally, in the FP scenario, the social welfare is slightly higher than in the Nash-Cournot equilibrium, at 627,022.4€, an increase of 1.1% (though still 2.21% lower than in the competitive market scenario). Due to the iterative joint learning process, DAs bid more effectively, ultimately lowering their electricity costs by 7.7% compared to the diagonalization algorithm, amounting to 341,046€ (15.34% lower than in the competitive market scenario) and thus depleting generators' net profits by 26.38%. Studying Figure 3, which illustrates the comparison between demand bids in FP scenario with those in the competitive market scenario, one can infer that DAs manage to significantly lower their costs during the early and late hours, while shifting consumption to the intermediate hours. As illustrated in Figure 4, this behavior results in decreased System Marginal Prices in most hours.

C. CONVERGENCE ANALYSIS

In this section, we present the convergence properties of the two models, namely the diagonalization (DIAG) and the FP. To this end, in addition to the 6-Bus test system described earlier, we conducted simulation tests on an 8-zone model of the ISO New England system [39]. This test system, which spans six U.S. states, comprises of 76 thermal generators with a total installed capacity of approximately 23 GW. Each zone is represented as a separate bus, and we assume that the load in each zone corresponds to a distinct DA in the electricity market. The system's total peak demand is about 18 GW. Detailed data on generation, load, and transmission can be found in [38].

FIGURE 2. Diagonalization algorithm demand bids.

FIGURE 3. Fictitious play algorithm demand bids.

FIGURE 4. Comparison of system marginal prices.

Figures 5 and 6 present the convergence behavior of each one of the solution approaches for the two case studies. Note that the y-axis in each of these plots shows each DA’s market cost, normalized by dividing each cost by its minimum value throughout all iterations. Figure 5 contains four lines, one for each DA, while Figure 6 includes eight lines, corresponding to the eight DAs, both illustrating the evolution of market

FIGURE 5. Convergence analysis - 6 bus test system.

FIGURE 6. Convergence analysis - 8 Zone new england test system.

costs over 100 iterations. We assume convergence in case all DAs’ costs do not change over 1% from an algorithm iteration to the next one.

DIAG iteratively optimizes each strategic DA’s decision, while keeping the strategies of competitors fixed. This approach exhibits poor convergence in our setting due to several inter-related factors. The strong strategic inter-dependencies among DAs cause significant fluctuations in market outcomes. Since each DA updates its strategy in response to the latest best-response of competitors, the market conditions change drastically between iterations, preventing stabilization. On top of that, EPEC’s non-convexities incur DIAG algorithm’s oscillations between competing strategies without settling on a stable solution. In non-convex environments, best-response updates do not necessarily lead to a monotonic improvement in the system’s equilibrium properties, leading to divergence or slow cycling behavior. The absence of averaging mechanisms in diagonalization amplifies these fluctuations. Since each DA does not consider the entire history of play, abrupt shifts in bidding and offering decisions occur, increasing instability and preventing convergence.

On the other hand, when each DA updates its beliefs gradually based on historical empirical distributions of competitors’ strategies (i.e., in the FP case), the collective strategies’ evolution is much smoother. Unlike DIAG, where players react to the latest best-response, FP assumes that each rival follows a stationary mixed strategy, refining these expectations over time. This structure introduces an implicit averaging effect, where strategy adjustments are smoothed over multiple iterations. The reliance on empirical frequencies rather than immediate responses prevents extreme shifts in offers and bids, facilitating a more stable learning process.

In summary, our numerical results from both case studies indicate distinct convergence behaviors, with DIAG exhibiting no tendency to converge within the first 100 iterations, while the FP exhibits exponential convergence.

VI. CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

This paper considered the problem of analyzing imperfect market equilibria in the presence of strategic Demand Aggregators (DAs). In contrast to the related literature, which models players either as myopic best-responders or as model-free learners, we argued that real players would try to optimize their profits by making the best of both worlds: they would make use of all available information about the market mechanism and their competitors, while learning (non-myopically) from the entire history of play. To that end, we proposed the Coarse Correlated Equilibrium (CCE) as a solution concept that is more relevant than the Nash Equilibrium (NE) for this setting, and proposed an MPEC-enhanced Fictitious Play (FP) algorithm to model the emergent market outcome. FP provides a straightforward approach for modeling learning dynamics in oligopolistic electricity markets. It captures how market participants adapt to the observed behaviors of competitors, offering valuable insights into how DAs approach strategic decision-making.

Simulations in a nodal day-ahead electricity market compared NE and CCE across four important metrics: social welfare, DA costs, generators' profits and system marginal prices. The respective numerical results provide valuable policy insights as follows:

- The Total Cost of DAs is lower in the CCE case. This suggests that, under the proposed - more pragmatic - model, strategic DAs can exert greater market influence than previously anticipated by the state-of-the-art EPEC models. A direct implication is that, as demand aggregators concentrate large portfolios of the rapidly penetrating DERs, the supply side will be exposed to profit losses (to a greater extent than the NE model predicts). Indeed, our results confirm that conventional generators' profit margins would be considerably decreased, and this could be seen as an opportunity for policy makers to better and more proactively design the smooth "phase-out" process of the most expensive and environment-unfriendly generation assets in the medium/long-term.
- Interestingly, while the resulting CCE exhibits greater market influence/manipulation by the strategic DAs (compared to the NE model), this does not mean greater Social Welfare loss. On the contrary, the Social Welfare at the resulting CCE is higher than in the NE. The straightforward interpretation of this is that the increased market influence by the DAs, acts as a counter-force to the generators' market power, partially counteracting it (cf. the respective decrease in generators' profit margin). This is also evident in the resulting System Marginal Prices, which are generally decreased in the CCE model.

- Existing multi-agent learning methods for strategic bidding and market equilibrium analysis (cf. subsection II-C) follow the current regulatory framework and are based on the assumption that each strategic DA only knows its own bid history and, based on each bid, it gets a reward/cost from the market. However, our model demonstrates that, if the DAs knew the bidding history of their rivals, the market could find itself in a CCE trajectory which, as described, exhibits different properties than existing NE models. Thereby, we presume that policy makers would opt for taking these results into account when deciding upon the frequency and granularity of past bidding data publication. Namely, a more frequent and granular data publication could result, as our model suggests, in lower total DA costs and lower system marginal prices. This might be desirable for making the DA's business more financially sustainable and accelerating new investments in distributed flexibility, which are vital for the quick and smooth energy transition process.
- Finally, the proposed model can constitute an additional tool for the regulator to assess potential market manipulation, in cases where existing models cannot identify. As future work, the envisioned tool could be expanded towards building a controlled market simulation environment (i.e. regulatory sandbox), via which a regulator/policy maker can test and experiment with various market settings and real-life data. In fact, there are ongoing regulatory discussions and legislative efforts at an international level towards obliging market operators to publish continuously more detailed data about

TABLE 4. Hourly loads generation dispatch results for generators G1, G2, G3, and G4 in competitive algorithm.

MTU	Total Load	G1	G2	G3	G4
1	211.619	100	75	36.619	0.000
2	200.595	100	75	25.595	0.000
3	175.000	100	75	0.000	0.000
4	196.222	100	75	21.222	0.000
5	175.000	100	75	0.000	0.000
6	225.000	100	75	50.000	0.000
7	225.000	100	75	50.000	0.000
8	246.918	100	75	50.000	21.918
9	247.237	100	75	50.000	22.237
10	258.482	100	75	50.000	33.482
11	224.921	100	75	49.921	0.000
12	224.857	100	75	49.857	0.000
13	224.843	100	75	49.843	0.000
14	224.826	100	75	49.826	0.000
15	224.426	100	75	49.426	0.000
16	224.802	100	75	49.802	0.000
17	247.257	100	75	50.000	22.257
18	246.514	100	75	50.000	21.514
19	236.853	100	75	50.000	11.853
20	232.736	100	75	50.000	7.736
21	226.695	100	75	50.000	1.695
22	245.180	100	75	50.000	20.180
23	225.000	100	75	50.000	0.000
24	225.000	100	75	50.000	0.000

TABLE 5. Hourly loads generation dispatch results for generators G1, G2, G3, and G4 in diagonalization algorithm.

MTU	Total Load	G1	G2	G3	G4
1	188.196	100	75	13.196	0
2	174.987	100	74.987	0	0
3	187.132	100	75	12.132	0
4	156.045	100	56.045	0	0
5	169.135	100	69.135	0	0
6	212.777	100	75	37.777	0
7	227.942	100	75	50	2.942
8	240.010	100	75	50	15.010
9	251.747	100	75	50	26.747
10	254.265	100	75	50	29.265
11	219.978	100	75	44.978	0
12	227.256	100	75	50	2.256
13	222.385	100	75	47.385	0
14	223.394	100	75	48.394	0
15	203.151	100	75	28.151	0
16	215.305	100	75	40.305	0
17	228.417	100	75	50	3.417
18	253.934	100	75	50	28.934
19	235.000	100	75	50	10.000
20	225.000	100	75	50	0
21	235.000	100	75	50	9.996
22	235.004	100	75	50	10.004
23	225.000	100	75	50	0
24	201.485	100	75	26.485	0

TABLE 6. Hourly loads generation dispatch results for generators G1, G2, G3, and G4 in fictitious play algorithm.

MTU	Total Load	G1	G2	G3	G4
1	225.000	100	75	50	0
2	175.000	100	75	0	0
3	175.000	100	75	0	0
4	175.000	100	75	0	0
5	175.000	100	75	0	0
6	175.000	100	75	0	0
7	225.000	100	75	50	0
8	275.000	100	75	50	50
9	225.000	100	75	50	0
10	255.019	100	75	50	30.019
11	245.612	100	75	50	20.612
12	214.412	100	75	39.412	0
13	249.105	100	75	50	24.105
14	212.655	100	75	37.655	0
15	224.946	100	75	49.946	0
16	209.339	100	75	34.339	0
17	254.289	100	75	50	29.289
18	275.000	100	75	50	50
19	225.000	100	75	50	0
20	225.000	100	75	50	0
21	225.000	100	75	50	0
22	225.000	100	75	50	0
23	261.144	100	75	50	36.144
24	175.000	100	75	0	0

historical (aggregated) bidding and offer curves as well as forecast generation/load data and ex-post market results across more granular timeslots and geographical areas. In this context, we aim at empirically validating the proposed CCE concept and our initial proof-of-concept results by also quantifying how different levels of information exposure (by the market operator) affect the CCE outcomes.

APPENDIX
TOTAL LOAD AND DISPATCHES IN EACH ALGORITHM

See Tables 4–6.

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